

MELON SEED PRODUCTION IN UZBEKISTAN: PROBLEMS, SOLUTIONS AND STATE SUPPORT

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Abstract. *Melon cultivation is an important agricultural sector in Uzbekistan, significantly impacting the population's living standards and export potential. However, the shortage of high-quality seeds remains a challenge. Although the use of certified seeds can increase yields by 15–30%, farmers often rely on ordinary, uncertified seeds. This negatively affects both product quality and income. The article analyzes issues related to seed quality, germination, storage conditions, and government support. It also provides recommendations for the development of the seed sector.*

Keywords: *melon, seed, certified seed, yield, state support, Uzbekistan.*

Introduction. Melon crops are considered strategically important sectors of agriculture in Uzbekistan. They have a direct impact on the population's lifestyle, public health, and the potential for increasing exports. However, the quality and quantity of melon products today largely depend on key factors within the seed production sector, among which the use of certified seeds plays a critical role.

Certified seeds are scientifically produced, genetically pure, environmentally sustainable, disease-resistant, and capable of delivering high yields. Nevertheless, the tradition of using ordinary (non-certified) seeds remains widespread among farmers. This continues to result in lower yields, reduced product quality, and limited export opportunities.

Analysis and methods. The seed is the foundation of any crop, and its quality determines the outcomes of the entire cultivation process. Numerous studies have shown that using certified seeds can increase yields by up to 15–30%. For instance, A.T. Aitbayeva and others found that when certified seeds were used in combination with organic and biological fertilizers, melon yields could reach up to 24.21 tons per hectare. [1].

However, at present, a large portion of the seeds used by farmers in our country are uncertified — consisting mostly of ordinary crop seeds. These seeds commonly exhibit the following shortcomings:

- Low level of genetic purity;
- Reduced germination capacity;
- Susceptibility to diseases;
- Low yield potential.

Figure 1. Factors that impact to productivity

As shown in Figure 1, several key factors influence crop yield. Among them, soil fertility and seed quality have the greatest significance, as evidenced by their high degree of impact on productivity.

The quality of seeds plays a crucial role in the yield of melon crops. The use of scientifically developed seeds not only increases productivity but also contributes to the long-term sustainability of agricultural production and enhances food security.

Challenges of the Current System. The existing seed production system faces several fundamental challenges, including:

- Insufficient availability of certified seeds;
- Lack of attention from farmers toward certified seed usage;
- Absence of adequate financial incentive mechanisms provided by the state;
- Seed production institutions not being adapted to modern technologies;
- A certification system that does not comply with international standards.

The **germination capacity** of melon seeds depends on several factors, including **temperature, humidity, storage conditions**, and the **initial quality** of the seeds.

Results and Discussion. Among these, **low temperatures** are a primary limiting factor. For effective germination, the soil temperature must not fall below **15°C**, as melon seeds require warmth for optimal sprouting. During the storage period, **high temperatures, excessive humidity, and improper storage methods** can lead to a decline in seed germination rates by up to **30% within six months**. In contrast, **high-quality seeds** can maintain their germination capacity for up to **six years** under optimal conditions. However, their planting quality tends to decline **after 18 months**. The best yields are typically achieved from seeds that have been stored for **one year**, which also results in **higher fruit quality**.

The **main objective of seed production** is to **preserve varietal purity**. Therefore, the **storage, placement, and cultivation** technologies for crops intended for seed production must prevent both **mechanical** and **biological contamination** of the variety. To avoid biological contamination, it is advisable that each seed production farm cultivates **only one variety** of melon crop. If two or three varieties of the same crop are grown simultaneously, it is essential to follow the **spatial isolation standards** outlined in **Table 1**.

Table 1.

Isolation distance.

Varieties of crops	In open areas (m)	In covered areas (m)
Melon crops	1000	500
Watermelon crops	2000	1000
Gourd crops	50	20

The importance of state support. active involvement of the state in the seed production sector ensures the sustainable development of the industry. in this regard, the following measures are of particular importance:

- subsidies: providing subsidies to farmers for purchasing certified seeds.
- modernization of research institutes: equipping seed laboratories with new technologies.
- international cooperation: utilizing the experience of leading countries in the field of seed production.
- improvement of the certification system: implementing a monitoring system in line with international standards

On September 5, 2019, in accordance with the decree of the president of the republic of Uzbekistan no. pf-5708 dated April 17, 2019, the cabinet of ministers adopted resolution no. 733. this resolution outlines the development of a “national seed policy” that meets international standards, as well as short- and long-term strategies aimed at improving the seed sector. it also includes measures to establish seed production clusters through public-private partnerships, support and develop small seed enterprises, and create a national brand called “Uzbek seeds.”

Table 2.

The amount of subsidies allocated from the state budget to the agricultural sector, billion sum (uzb)

as seen in table 2, in 2022, a total of 1,384.3 billion Uzbek sums in subsidies were allocated from the state budget to support the development of the agricultural sector, which is 88 billion sums more than in 2021.

Table 3.

Directions of subsidies allocated in 2022.

Directions of subsidies	Amount (billion. sum)	Percentage, %
Total allocated	1 384,3	100,0%
Drip irrigation system for cotton	71,3	5,15%
Water-saving technologies for other crops	5,2	0,38%
Water-saving technologies in gardens and vineyards	105,7	7,64%
Drip irrigation and artesian wells for industrial viticulture	14,3	1,03%
Support for the livestock (fish, poultry) sector	477,8	34,54%
Digging wells on private property	95,6	6,91%
Well and drip irrigation system in orchards(tutzorlar)	4,9	0,35%
Encouragement of home-grown silkworms	120,2	8,69%
Encourage the purchase of agricultural machinery	66,6	4,81%
Electricity for water pumps on farms	244,0	17,63%
To restore the land to a cultivable state	92,6	6,69%
Other directions	86,1	6,22%

As shown in table 3, in 2022, the allocated funds were distributed among various sectors of agriculture. a significant portion was provided to livestock and poultry farms, and considerable financial support was also directed toward farmers' electricity expenses for water pumps. the table indicates that substantial attention was paid to water-saving technologies in different agricultural sectors. however, the lack of funds allocated specifically to the seed sector suggests that this area is not receiving sufficient targeted attention.

Conclusion. the seed sector for melon and other gourd crops in uzbekistan is a pressing issue that requires wide-ranging reforms to achieve sustainable development. although using certified seeds can increase yields by 15–30%, uncertified and conventional seeds are still commonly used by farmers. this limits product quality, productivity, and export potential. to develop the seed sector, active government involvement, incentives for farmers, scientific and technical support, and improvement of the certification system based on international experience are essential. therefore, comprehensive measures must be implemented to advance this sector. the following are key recommendations in this regard:

- encourage farmers to use certified seeds;
- provide tax incentives and attract investment for biofertilizer production;
- align research institutes with international standards;
- localize production of f1 hybrid varieties;
- attract foreign investors to the seed production sector;
- automate the seed certification process.

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